

CREATIVE APPROACH AND ITS EFFICIENCY IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTIONS STUDENT SPEECH DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: *The article provides a scientific analysis of the issues aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the creative approach and the development of speech and thinking of students of higher education institutions.*

Keywords: *creative approach, speech, external motivation, creative potential, cognition, developing students' speech*

Particular attention is paid to the effective use of educational technologies based on a creative approach in various areas of development around the world, the development of speech and thinking of students of higher education institutions in the context of informatization of education. It is also important to carry out educational activities in higher education institutions on the basis of a creative approach, to ensure the integration of students' speech and thinking, which integrates and develops their thinking.

In the context of modernization of the process of speech development and development of thinking of students of higher education institutions, the mechanism of implementation of innovative activities and promising technologies, the use of modern information and communication technologies, the success of the innovation process depends on the creative approach of teachers. We know that any innovation in the education system cannot be an idea, an idea, an innovation. The clear form, content and scope of reform activities serve as a basis for this. It should be noted that one of the important indicators of the development of speech and thinking of students in higher education is the ability of the teacher to motivate students, which has a direct positive impact on the educational process. Motivational arousal not only creates a favorable environment for student development and social adaptation, but also supports the student's creative abilities, ensuring the interdependence of all types of developmental areas in the learning process.

From a pedagogical point of view, motivation is a teacher's curiosity about his profession. It is hard to say that a teacher who does not love his profession, who is not interested in his profession, is ideally engaged in creative activities. The following forms of motivation have been identified in science:

- External motivation - as a result of social influences, a person is directed to a particular activity. Today, in all types of continuing education, as well as in the higher education system, educational work is organized with the use of pedagogical technologies and various forms of didactic systems, enriched with innovative innovations. This, in turn,

requires each educator to reconsider and organize his professional activity, that is, to have a creative nature of pedagogical activity;

- Internal motivation - is the desire, needs and interests of teachers to ensure their functioning. Along with the development of individual and professional qualities that meet the new didactic requirements, a deep understanding of the content of the pedagogical profession, the positive motivational training of teachers to effectively organize their profession is of great importance.

- have an internal motive in the structure of motives of pedagogical activity;
- motivation to achieve results;
- Motivation of the teacher aimed at self-development;

Objectives of the state requirements: to determine the requirements for the development, content and quality of education of students of higher education institutions; introduction of effective forms and methods of education and upbringing of students on the basis of national, universal and spiritual values; introduction of pedagogical and modern information and communication technologies in the educational process; ensuring effective integration of education, science and industry for targeted and quality training of personnel.

The formation of the creative potential of teachers working in higher education institutions involves several stages. These are:

Step 1. At this stage, educators are given ready methodological guidelines;

Step 2. This includes some additions (modifications) and methodological recommendations to the finished material and systems;

Step 3. The content, methods, forms of implementation of the new idea will be fully developed;

Step 4. At this stage, a unique concept and methodology of teaching and education is created

In our opinion, through the implementation of a new idea, training can achieve the following levels of development of creative competence:

- Productivity, ie the importance of the creativity of the developed innovations;
- Raising issues related to the solution of various issues in the pedagogical process;
- recommend original solutions; - to continue or find other options for solutions or pedagogical approaches that can be solved, etc.

In higher education, students are required not only to have specific knowledge, but also to have the ability to think, to understand the speech of peers and adults, to communicate freely with them, to work on a collaborative basis. It is important for students to think logically, express their ideas correctly through speech, control themselves, manage, observe, hear, remember, generalize, compare, and perform thinking operations. In fulfilling this task, of course, speech development activities are of great importance. In the following, we have concluded that the tasks of developing students' speech and developing their thinking based on a creative approach in activities can be described in the following view.

To know	Educational	Educational	Developer
Tasks to grow students' speech and develop their thinking			
Enriching students' vocabulary	Grammatically enriching speech	Nurturing speech by breathing	To cultivate speech with fiction

In the above, in the process of any cognitive activity in the educational process, both methods and methods were used. Teaching methods are the concrete interaction of teachers and students in the use of teaching methods. With the help of teaching methods, some of the tasks underlying the teaching method are performed. The same methods can be used on the basis of different methods. Or conversely, the same method can also be disclosed using different methods. The method is described as an integral part of the teaching method, an important element of it, as a separate step in the introduction of the method. Each teaching method is introduced by comparing specific teaching methods. Teaching methods are the basis for using the method. Each method involves several methods. In educational practice, as the most widely used methods, which are covered at the core of many methods: demonstration, demonstration, experiment, practical, mental action; study the issue; ask a question or assignment; mentoring serves to develop students' thinking.